

fax message

To: Matt Pritchard
Company: NERC EODC, IIAL
Fax No. 01235 445841
CC:

Infoterra Ltd.
Delta House, Southwood Crescent,
Southwood, Farnborough,
Hampshire, GU14 0NL
United Kingdom.
T. +44 (0) 1252 362000
F. +44 (0) 1252 375016
E. info@infoterra-global.com
www.infoterra-global.com

From: Sheena Wing
Email: sheena.wing@infoterra-global.com
Direct line: +44 (0)1252 362080
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Subject: RAE Format

Dear Matt

Thanks for your email. The following information may be of help to you. If not, let me know and I'll try and think of something else.

Best regards,

Sheena

RAE format spec
(Landsat)

RAE format for
(Lambert)

RAE C/T TAPE FORMAT SPECIFICATION

All data archived at the NRSC, irrespective of satellite or sensor, are converted to a standard format, known as the RAE format. Data can be supplied to customers in the ground station format or this standard RAE format. The tape specification for the RAE format is detailed below.

Each image is written on 9-track, 1600 or 6250 bpi magnetic tapes and uses ANSI standard tape labels. The tapes, which may be both multi-file and multi-volume, will be organised in the manner shown in Figure 1.

The contents of the four ANSI standard tape labels, VOL 1, HDR 1, EOF 1 and EOY 1 are shown in Table 1, each of these will be 80 characters (bytes) in length and written in ASCII code.

The first data record will be a header. This contains general identification information and specifies the number and size of the image records. The contents and formats of the header and data records are shown in Tables 2 and 3 respectively.

Figure 1 : Tape Structure

Table 1 : YOL 1, HDR 1, EOF 1 AND EOY Label Contents

Label	Character position	Name	Length	Description
YOL 1	1-3	Label identifier	3	YOL
	4	Label number	1	1
	5-10	Volume serial number	6	Six character tape identification number
	11	Accessibility	1	'Space'
	12-31	Reserved	20	'Spaces'
	32-37	Reserved	6	'Spaces'
	38-51	Owner identification	14	RAE IMAGE TAPE
	80	Label standard level	1	1
HDR 1	1-3	Label identifier	3	HDR
	4	Label number	1	1
	5-21	File identifier	17	IDP3000 IMAGE left justified
	22-27	Set identification	6	Same as YOL 1, volume serial number
	28-31	File section number	4	The file section No of the first header label of each file is 0001. This applies to the first or only file on a volume and to subsequent file on a multi-file volume. This file is incremented by one on each subsequent volume of the file
	32-35	File sequence number	4	Four characters denoting the sequence of files within a volume or set of volumes. In all labels for a given file, this field will contain the same number
	36-39	Generation number	4	0001
	40-41	Generation version No	2	00
	42-47	Creation date	6	A 'space' followed by two characters for the year and three characters for the day (001 to 366) within the year
	48-53	Expiration date	6	Same format as Creation Date
	54	Accessibility	1	'Space'
	55-60	Block count	6	000000
61-73	System code	13	PRIME 400 left justified	
74-80	Reserved	7	'Spaces'	
EOF 1	1-3	Label identifier	3	EOF
	4	Label number	1	1
	5-54	Same as fields in HDR 1	50	Same as corresponding fields in HDR 1
	55-60	Block count	6	Six numerical characters denoting the number of data blocks (exclusive of labels and tape marks) since the preceding HDR 1 label
61-80	Same as fields in HDR 1	20	Same as corresponding fields in HDR 1	
EOY 1	1-3	Label identifier	3	EOY
	4	Label number	1	1
	5-54	same as fields in HDR 1	50	Same as corresponding fields in HDR 1
	55-60	Block count	6	Six numerical characters denoting the number of data blocks (exclusive of labels and tape marks) since the preceding HDR 1 label
61-80	Same as fields in HDR 1	20	Same as corresponding fields in HDR 1	

Table 2 : Contents of the Header Record

Byte	Name	Type	Description
1-8	Reserved	ASCII	Blanks
9-12	Reserved	ASCII	Blanks
13-14	Pixel length	ASCII	Number of bytes (n) per pixel
15-16	Length of image data record	BINARY	Number of pixels (p) in each data record. Each data record will be of length $m = n \times p$ bytes
17-18	Number of image data records	BINARY	Number of lines in the image
19-98	Image description	ASCII	Image location and origin
99-200	Filler	BINARY	all ones (these locations may be filled with further ancillary data if required)
201-2248	Reserved	ASCII	Reference information*

Table 3 : Contents of the Image Data Records

Byte	Name	Type	Description
1 - n	PIXEL	BINARY	Radiance level corresponding to the ith pixel in this line of data
n + 1 - 2n		BINARY	
⋮	⋮		
⋮	⋮		
⋮	⋮		
(i-1)n + 1 - in	BINARY		
⋮	RADIANCE LEVELS	⋮	
⋮		⋮	
⋮		⋮	
⋮		⋮	
(p-1)n + 1 - m		BINARY	

NOTE: For multi-spectral imagery the data from each spectral band is recorded in a separate file.

factors

① (A13475)
21812608

-2248 = 21810360

prime factors $\rightarrow$ (2³) (3) (5) 11 13 31 (41)

$\rightarrow 2^3 \times 3 \times 5 \times 41 = 4920$

$\rightarrow 11 \times 13 \times 31 = 4433$

(A13476)

② 20047384 -2248 = 20045136

PF $\rightarrow 2^4 \times 3 \times 179 \times 2333$

4666 $\times$ 4296

(A13477)

③ 20083248 -2248 = 20081000

PF $\rightarrow 2^3 \times 5^3 \times 43 \times 467$

eg 4670 $\times$ 4300 ✓ !!